

Instructions for the Experiment

How to Install the Required Plugin for the Experiment

Install the latest version of Google Chrome (89.0.4389.114), Firefox (87.0) or any Chromium variant that supports installing Chrome extensions (e.g. Edge, Vivaldi, Opera, etc.).

Navigate to the Violentmonkey extension installation page (Chrome or Firefox) and click Use in Chrome or Firefox Only — Install Firefox now. This step may vary if you are using a browser other than Chrome or Firefox. In this scenario, search for: How to install Chrome extensions in <your-browser-name> and return to the beginning of step 2.

Chrome:

Firefox:

Navigate to the script page <ANONYMIZED DUE TO DOUBLE BLIND> and click Raw:

After clicking, a new page will open where Violentmonkey will ask for a script installation confirmation. Click Confirm Installation. Then click Close or close the tab.

To check that the script is working as expected, navigate to the page: <https://<ANONYMIZED DUE TO DOUBLE BLIND>>. If you don't see lines saying: "the-funnel-bot deleted a comment from (...)", the script is working and you are ready to continue with the experiment.

fixed add function #1

If the script is not working:

fixed add function #1

Check if you have any extensions enabled that block scripts from running on the page (e.g. uBlock Origin, NoScript, etc). If so, disable it during the experiment.

Make sure you have blocked scripts from running in your browser settings: [How to Disable \(and Enable\) JavaScript in Google Chrome \(howtogeek.com\)](#). If so, disable it during the experiment.

Try installing the script again following step 3.